

Focus group briefing: Collections as Data infrastructures

Researching the Future of Museum Collections symposium hosted by Deakin University (Melbourne) on the 22nd-23rd of November 2023

Overview

This focus group discussion will explore the interests and needs of cultural heritage institutions in Collections as Data infrastructure projects.

After decades of mass digitisation in the cultural heritage sector the attention moves towards leveraging digitised collections in ways unique to data, such as text mining, network analysis, and machine learning.¹ The expectations on the possibilities of Collections as Data are high: researchers in the arts and humanities seek to respond to new and old questions through the means of data; the creative sector leverages collections data for artistic interventions; commercial firms create new business models; and governments seek to boost the digital economy. Some heritage institutions respond to these trends locally by setting up GLAM Labs: agile innovation units for experimenting with collections data, technology and services.²

European governments invest on a national and pan-national scale in programmes for creating large scale infrastructures for collections data dissemination and unification. In the United Kingdom through the 'Towards a National Collection' (TaNC) programme and in the European Union through 'the common European data space for cultural heritage'. The latter is led by the Europeana Foundation and "[...] will link to relevant European, national and regional initiatives and platforms, providing interoperable access to cultural heritage data".³ In Australia, the National Infrastructure Roadmap⁴ has recognised the importance of collections as a part of the national research infrastructure and sees digitisation as a means to develop a co-ordinated national approach to ensuring collections can be accessed for research purposes. The Australian Academy of Humanities⁵ too sees opportunities for building collaboration between the GLAM sector and researchers in the

¹ Padilla, T. (2017). On a Collections as Data Imperative. UC Santa Barbara <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/9881c8sv> (accessed 5 February 2020). Padilla, T., Allen, L., Frost, H., Potvin, S., Russey Roke, E. and Varner, S. (2019). Santa Barbara Statement on Collections as Data --- Always Already Computational: Collections as Data Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/record/3066209> (accessed 1 February 2021).

² Mahey, M., Al-Abdulla, A., Ames, S., Bray, P., Candela, G., Chambers, S., Derven, C., et al. (2019). Open a GLAM Lab. Digital Cultural Heritage Innovation Labs. Doha: Book Sprint <https://assets.pubpub.org/4kaopqbk/31574367506714.pdf> (accessed 7 December 2021).

³ Europeana Pro (2023). Data space - deployment <https://pro.europeana.eu/page/data-space-deployment> (accessed 4 July 2023).

⁴ Department of Education, Skills and Employment (2022). 2021 National Research Infrastructure Roadmap <https://www.dese.gov.au/national-research-infrastructure/resources/2021-national-research-infrastructure-roadmap> (accessed 3 October 2023).

⁵ Australian Academy of the Humanities (2022). Australia's Data-enabled Research Future: Humanities <https://humanities.org.au/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/Australias-Data-Enabled-Research-Future-Humanities.pdf> (accessed 3 October 2023).

Humanities and Social sciences so as to better utilise collections in research about culture and resilience.

TaNC and the data space are high-level views on infrastructure development. In this focus group we seek to explore the institutional perspectives, needs and interests in Collections as Data infrastructure developments. What is your experience with Collections as Data to date? Where does Collections as Data sit within your institutional priorities? What kind of activities are needed to support your organisation in facilitating Collections as Data work? In this focus group we seek to find some responses to these questions. While we propose a set of questions, we welcome an open discussion on the topic and encourage you to feed in reflections from the symposium throughout the discussion. The Sloane Lab has already carried out surveys with the UK as well as the German heritage sector and we are interested to learn more how those findings relate to other national contexts, such as that of Australia. By carrying out this focus group we will be able to build a picture of the status quo in Australia and bring this into conversations with the findings of the previous studies.

Questionnaire

1. What are your institutions' experiences with Collections as Data on a practical or conceptual level?
2. Where do you situate Collections as Data work within your institutional priorities?
3. Which communities do you, or could you imagine you would like to, connect with through Collections as Data work?
4. Who are important stakeholders for facilitating Collections as Data work?
5. What kind of activities are needed to build collections data infrastructures in your organisation?
6. What do you see as some of the challenges you need to overcome to be able to do so?
7. What kind of activities are needed to build cross-institutional collections data infrastructures?
8. Is there anything we have not covered that you would like to talk about?